

OPTIMIZATION OF FILMS FOR ENHANCED BARRIER PROPERTIES OF BIODEGRADABLE PACKAGING

Yasaman Ghasemi¹, Mia Kurek², Maria-Jose Fabra³, Nasreddine Benbettaieb^{1,4} and Frédéric Debeaufort^{1,4}

¹Joint research unit UMR PAM, Université Bourgogne Europe, Institut Agro, INRAE, Dijon, France.

² Faculty of Food Technology and Biotechnology, University of Zagreb, Zagreb, Croatia

³ Instituto de Agroquímica y Tecnología de Alimentos (IATA), Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, C/ Catedrático Agustín Escardino 7, Paterna (Valencia), Spain.

⁴ Department of BioEngineering, IUT-Dijon-Auxerre, Université Bourgogne Europe, Dijon, France

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frederic.debeaufort@ube.fr

Abstract: *Fresh foods are sensitive to oxidation and spoilage. If sustainable biopackaging are wished, these require performing barrier properties that need to be optimized for instance by coating applications. Blending of hydrocolloids and other biopolymers to form interpenetrated network coatings is one of the strategies to improve oxygen and moisture barrier efficacy of cellulosic or biodegradable materials. Gelatin, psyllium, and zein have been associated to reach the permeability value targetted.*

Keywords: biodegradable packaging, barrier properties, oxygen permeability, water vapour permeability, surface wettability

1 INTRODUCTION

The environmental issue of plastic pollution has led the scientific community to explore sustainable alternatives, including edible films and coatings. These materials, made from natural biopolymers, have the advantage of being biodegradable, renewable, and sometimes functional, actively contributing to food preservation (Azeredo & Waldron, 2016; Pavlath & Orts, 2009). Among them, films based on gelatin, zein, and psyllium are attracting growing interest, each offering specific properties that are useful in the field of active and intelligent packaging.

Gelatin, derived from collagen, is widely studied for film manufacturing due to its good gelation properties and ability to form homogeneous polymer networks. It provides excellent transparency and good retention capacity for active additives (antioxidants, antimicrobials, freshness indicators (Chen et al., 2023; Sobral et al., 2001). However, its hydrophilic nature limits its mechanical strength and stability in humid conditions (Kchaou et al., 2018; Krishna et al., 2012). To overcome these limitations, gelatin is often combined with other more resistant or hydrophobic biopolymers. It is in this context that zein and psyllium are of strategic interest: the former for its barrier and rigidity properties, the latter for its fibrous and functional characteristics (Coltelli et al., 2016).

Zein is a prolamin protein derived from corn, characterized by a high content of non-polar amino acids (Lawton, 2002). This structure gives it a natural hydrophobicity that is rare among proteins, making it a major asset for food packaging. Unlike gelatin, zein forms films that are less sensitive to moisture

and provide an effective barrier against oxygen and fats (Ghanbarzadeh & Almasi, 2013). In addition, zein films are distinguished by their rigidity and good adhesion to food surfaces, making them suitable as protective coatings on fruit, confectionery, or meat (Lan et al., 2023). Their compatibility with aqueous-alcoholic solvents also facilitates the incorporation of lipophilic bioactive molecules (essential oils, polyphenols) into a stable matrix. Studies have shown that incorporating antioxidant-rich plant extracts (e.g., pomegranate or green tea) into zein films allows for controlled and prolonged release of the active compounds, helping to delay lipid oxidation in meat products (Figuerola-Lopez, Enescu, et al., 2020; Figuerola-Lopez, Torres-Giner, et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2022). It is therefore regularly considered as a coating solution for materials with very low barrier properties (Kansal et al., 2020). Another advantage is zein's ability to form nanoparticles and nanofibers via electrospinning, paving the way for smart, active films that can, for example, incorporate freshness indicators or encapsulated antimicrobials (Cheng et al., 2024).

Psyllium (*Plantago ovata*, *Plantago psyllium*) is a source of mucilage rich in soluble and insoluble polysaccharides. These polysaccharides, particularly arabinoxylan, form viscoelastic gels capable of retaining large amounts of water (Ahmadi et al., 2012). This property gives psyllium a remarkable ability to produce flexible films and improve the mechanical texture of composite films when combined with other polymers. The most distinctive contribution of psyllium is its ability to form fibrous networks that reinforce the cohesion and tensile strength of films (Krystyjan et al., 2017; Niknam et al., 2019). Recent work has explored the use of psyllium in synbiotic films, where it plays a dual role: film-forming matrix and prebiotic. For example, the combination of psyllium and other hydrocolloids has made it possible to develop edible films that can encapsulate live probiotics while maintaining their viability for fruit, meat or dairy products applications without sensory alteration (Aslan Kaya et al., 2025a, 2025b).

The combination of gelatin with zein and psyllium offers interesting prospects. Zein compensates for gelatin's low moisture resistance with its hydrophobic properties. Psyllium strengthens the mechanical structure and adds nutritional value to the films. Together, these biopolymers can be used to design multifunctional films (barrier, active, smart, nutritional) suitable for various food products.

The objective of our work is to evaluate the functional properties of gelatin-based coatings combined with zein or psyllium for paper impregnation.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Sample materials

Fish gelatin (Louis François, France), psyllium fiber (Louis François, France), glycerol (>99%, Sigma-Aldrich), ethanol (>99.7%, Sigma-Aldrich), acetic acid (>99.5%, Sigma-Aldrich), and zein (Sigma-Aldrich) were used for the preparation of biopolymer films. All reagents were of analytical grade and used without further purification.

2.2 Film making

A film-forming solution was prepared by dissolving 7.4 g of gelatin and 0.8 g of zein in 100 mL of 60% (v/v) aqueous acetic acid under continuous stirring until complete solubilization of the proteins. After dissolution, 1 g of glycerol was added as a plasticizer and thoroughly mixed into the solution.

For gelatin-psyllium films, 7.4 g of gelatin and 0.8 g of psyllium were dissolved in 100 mL of distilled water preheated to 60 °C. A few drops of acetic acid were added to adjust the pH, and the mixture was stirred until complete dispersion. Glycerol (1 g) was then incorporated under constant agitation.

Both film-forming solutions were cast onto non-stick square Petri dishes (12 × 12 cm) and left to dry under ambient conditions until complete solvent evaporation. The resulting films were carefully peeled off the casting surfaces and stored in desiccators for subsequent characterization. The average film thicknesses was measured using a digital caliper and values were for gelatin–zein 0.25±0.03 mm, for gelatin–psyllium 0.15±0.02 mm, and for gelatin 0.07±0.03 mm.

2.3 Film characterizations

All the characterizations have been done at 25°C and 50% RH as they refers to EU standards (ISO) and allow to mimic ambient conditions, and not to the US methods (ASTM).

The surface morphology of the films was examined after gold coating by sputtering using a scanning electron microscope using 5-15 kV and max 0.1Pa (SU1510, Hitachi, Japan) to observe structural features and homogeneity.

Mechanical properties were determined with a universal traction testing machine (TA.HD plus, Stable MicroSystems, England) equipped with a 300 N load cell, following the ISO 527-3. Rectangular specimens (2.5 × 8 cm²) were prepared with a precision cutter, equilibrated for two weeks at 25 °C and 50% RH, and stretched uniaxially at 50 mm/min until rupture; tensile strength (TS) and Young's modulus (YM) were calculated from the stress – strain curves, with five replicates per formulation tested at 25 ± 2 °C.

Water vapor permeability (WVP) was measured gravimetrically according to the standard method (ISO 2528 - International Standard Organisation, 2017) using a relative humidity gradient of 33–84% at 25 °C according to the method adapted for hydrophilic polymers (Debeaufort et al., 1993). The values were obtained by recording the weight loss of test cells sealed with the films and corrected for film thickness and vapor pressure difference.

Contact angle measurements were carried out with a DSA30 goniometer (Kruss, Germany) using eleven liquids of different polarities, including water, glycerol, ethylene glycol, ethanol (96% v/v), and selected binary mixtures (water–ethanol, water–ethylene glycol, and glycerol–ethanol) at varying ratios. Initial contact angles and their kinetics were recorded, and the surface free energy (SFE) of the films, including its polar and dispersive components, was calculated using the Owens–Wendt–Rabel–Kaelble (OWRK) method (Owens & Wendt, 1969). The critical surface tension (CST) of wetting was estimated according to Zisman's extrapolation method (Zisman, 1964).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As shown in Figure 1, the gelatin–psyllium forming solution exhibited markedly higher viscosity than the gelatin–zein system. This suggests that psyllium incorporation enhances solution thickness due to stronger intermolecular interactions and greater water-binding capacity compared to zein.

Figure 1: Viscosity of gelatin and gelatin based systems with additives (MPa.s)

Figure 2: SEM micrographs of gelatin–zein (left) and gelatin–psyllium (right) films at 1500× magnification

The SEM micrographs showed clear differences in surface morphology between the films. Gelatin–psyllium displayed a fibrous network structure, indicating that some psyllium fibers were not fully dissolved, with fibers measuring about 20 μm in width and 80 μm in length. In contrast, gelatin–zein presented dot-like domains, likely caused by phase separation due to the limited miscibility between hydrophilic gelatin and hydrophobic zein, resulting in small, precipitated particles of about 2–5 μm (Figure 2).

Figure 3: Tensile strength of gelatin–zein and gelatin–psyllium films

As shown in Figure 3, the mechanical properties of the films were strongly influenced by composition. Gelatin–zein films exhibited a much higher tensile strength (maximum stress at break = 366 MPa). For comparison, fish gelatin films without additional components have been reported to exhibit a tensile strength of only 4.3 ± 0.5 MPa, highlighting the reinforcing effect of both zein (>350 MPa) and psyllium (>150 MPa). Even if psyllium was less efficient than zein to increase tensile strength, it allowed to rise by almost 35 times gelatine-based films mechanical resistance to break. This suggests gelatin–zein films are better suited for applications requiring high mechanical durability, whereas gelatin–psyllium films, despite lower strength, may provide greater flexibility, which is beneficial where elasticity is desired.

The oxygen permeability of the films clearly depended on the film composition and structure. Gelatin–zein films showed the lowest oxygen permeability ($0.98 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{m} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{Pa}^{-1}$), indicating the best oxygen barrier, while gelatin–psyllium films were more permeable (2.46×10^{-12}). For comparison, pure gelatin had an even lower oxygen permeability of 0.148×10^{-12} . These results show that adding zein improves oxygen resistance compared to psyllium, making gelatin–zein films more suitable for protecting oxygen-sensitive foods (Figure 4). The water vapor permeability (WVP) values indicate that gelatin-zein films ($9.6 \times 10^{-11} \text{ g} \cdot \text{m} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{Pa}^{-1}$) have the lowest barrier to moisture transfer, followed by gelatin-psyllium (3.3×10^{-11}) and pure gelatin films (2.6×10^{-11}). It is most probable the particle dispersion of zein, though it is hydrophobic, does not affect the moisture transfer through the

continuous layer of gelatine, explaining why it is worst as a barrier. Moreover, psyllium also favoured the moisture transfer, maybe acting as a moisture absorbent. Overall, the results demonstrate that the choice of zein or psyllium addition in gelatin films cannot effectively modulate in the expected trend their moisture barrier properties.

Figure 4: Oxygen and water vapour permeability of films

Table 1: surface properties of films

Film name	Initial contact angle °	critical surface tension (mN·m ⁻¹)	Polar/dispersive ratio
Gelatin–Psyllium 10%	117	25.51	0.22
Gelatin–Zein 10%	124	18.77	0.06
Gelatin 10%	120	28.95	0.00

The surface properties of the films were also influenced by the incorporation of Psyllium or zein. Contact angle measurements, surface free energy (SFT), and the polar/dispersive component ratio indicated significant differences in wettability and surface characteristics. The higher critical surface tension of gelatin–psyllium (25.5 mN·m⁻¹) compared to gelatin–zein (18.9) suggests that gelatin–psyllium films are more hydrophilic, exhibiting higher water wettability, whereas gelatin–zein films seems slightly hydrophobic (Figure 5). Indeed, the higher the critical surface tension means liquids of about 30 mN·m⁻¹ are most suitable to spread and wet surface of films, and for instance, ethanol which value is 22 mN·m⁻¹ is most probable adapted to gelatin zein that is more hydrophobic. This is consistent with the observed contact angle and surface energy values, where the increased polar component in gelatin–psyllium enhances interactions with water, while the higher dispersive component in gelatin–zein reduces surface affinity toward polar liquids (Table 1).

Figure 5: critical surface tension of films

4 CONCLUSIONS

In summary, the incorporation of psyllium and zein into gelatin films produced distinct effects on their structural, mechanical, and barrier properties. Psyllium increased viscosity and generated a fibrous surface morphology, resulting in more flexible and hydrophilic films with greater water wettability, though at the expense of tensile strength and oxygen resistance. Conversely, zein enhanced mechanical strength and oxygen barrier properties, forming a more homogeneous but slightly hydrophobic structure. However, neither additive improved water vapor permeability in the expected manner, as both facilitated moisture transfer through the gelatin matrix. Overall, the choice between psyllium and zein depends on the intended application: gelatin–zein films are better suited for high-strength, oxygen-sensitive packaging, while gelatin–psyllium films may be advantageous where flexibility and hydrophilicity are desired.

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